

The probabilistic nature of quantum mechanics of a collection of interacting particles as an emergent phenomenon caused by intrinsic deterministic single elementary particles

Sometimes it is more important to ask the correct questions rather to give the correct answer. It has been proven for the last century beyond any shroud of doubt that the “Quantum World” is *collectively* probabilistic in nature as countless times proven by experiments and shown by theoretical analysis. This is also broadly communed to the general public via the media but also among the science community via the literature. Any attempts made by scientists today and in the past to prove that quantum mechanics, against the scientific consensus, as a deterministic mechanism has fallen to the void, dismissed and even ridiculed as unscientific and in most cases rightfully so, we must say since these were lacking in scientific rigour.

However, in this case this is not the correct question we should ask. Let us explain to set the record straight because it seems that there is confusion on what this probabilistic nature of the quantum is referring to, even among experts in the field. Quantum Mechanics and the Standard Model were developed as a framework in theoretical and experimental quantum physics for studying and researching the physics of particle(s) or else referred as quantum field excitations in Quantum Field Theory, by theoretical and or experimental research of a *collection of particles* as a closed system. We emphasize here the words *collection of particles* meaning that all the so called non-intuitive “quantum weirdness” like the Heisenberg Uncertainty Principle, Quantum Entanglement, Quantum Tunneling etc., we have discovered by researching and inherent from a collection of particles, many-bodies system and not by studying the individual isolated single elementary particles.

With other words, the probabilistic nature of quantum mechanics and the related probabilistic phenomena mentioned above refer to the interaction of a collection of quantum particles as emergent phenomena from this interaction **and in no way** it is inferred or predicted by

Quantum Mechanics anywhere and experimentally proven until today, that this **emergent probabilistic property of quantum interactions is intrinsic to the single elementary particle(s)**.

Therefore, Quantum Mechanics and the Standard Model does not make any predictions or give experimental results about what the nature of *single isolated elementary particle(s)* could be and their possible intrinsic mechanics?

Meaning as strongly inferred almost conclusively also by the *measurement problem* and the *double slit* experiment:

That interactions mechanics among particles are probabilistic but the particles itself, intrinsic mechanics are deterministic in nature?

That is the correct question we believe someone should be asking and deserves the outmost interest from the science community and is key for the future of quantum physics in general.

A single isolated elementary particle at rest, examined having no translational motion could have very much so, deterministic intrinsic mechanics and the SM *does not* predict what this mechanics would be?

Furthermore, the possible deterministic nature of single isolated closed system elementary particles are also strongly inferred from our consistent experience of measuring very accurately the fixed values of their intrinsic properties like charge, mass, magnetic moment etc. If ontologically, single elementary particles would be probabilistic in nature then why are we measuring these same exact values every time we measure them? This surely infers to a deterministic *mechanics* behavior.

Finally, this above question highlighted in bold, will also bring balance among determinists and hard core status quo scientists in the community and an end to a many years dispute that will favor the progress of physics and our understanding of the quantum world and its impact at the macroscopic. As we going from the quantum scale to the macroscopic, particles interact more and more with their environment decoherence takes place via the increased entanglement and the macroscopic world becomes deterministic. It is funny if you think about the root matter takes, deterministic single elementary particles to collection of probabilistic interacting particles to macroscopic deterministic objects.

Under this context and field of research described above, comes also our pioneering current research we present for peer-review to the physics community:

A topology for the electron

<http://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.4590887>

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